

**ANALYSIS OF OPERATIONAL CONDITION OF BRIDGES AND OVERPASSES IN
TASHKENT CITY**

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U.Z. Shermuxamedov

DSc, professor, ,

M.M. Sobirova¹

doctoral student

I.F. Khikmatova

doctoral student ¹

A.R. Abdullayev

doctoral student Tashkent State Transport University

Abstract: *The results of the study and analysis of the current state of the reinforced concrete bridges in operation on the roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The technical condition of bridges operating on public roads of the country was analyzed.*

Keywords: *bridges and overpasses, artificial structures, reinforced concrete bridges, operation, monitoring system, diagnostics, megacity, balance keepers.*

Introduction. The importance of the transport logistics system in the modern global economy is increasing significantly. And as a fundamental part of the logistic system, it is possible to identify road signs, bridges, tunnels and other artificial structures, constructions and roads.

The large-scale creative work carried out in the field of architecture and construction in our country creates opportunities for our people, first of all, for our children. Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2017 №. PP-3309 "On improving the system for organizing the construction and operation of road bridges, overpasses and other artificial structures", dated March 29, 2018 №. PP-3632 "On approval of the program for the construction, reconstruction and capital repair of road bridges, overpasses and other artificial structures in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and the city of Tashkent for 2018-2022" and dated December 9, 2019 № PP-4545 "On measures to further improve the management system of the road industry" [1-3] are an important programmatic step in raising the work in this regard to a new level. In the

country, a number of design organizations and construction organizations are work on the design and construction of bridge structures.

Main part. In fulfillment of these tasks, at the beginning of 2019, an inventory of bridge structures on the roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan was carried out. Currently, more than 7,000 road bridges are in operation on the public roads of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the results of the inventory, the total number of bridges on the roads of the country is 14331, including 604 - international, 2722 - republican, 4302 - local, 6703 urban and rural roads. It is known that most of the bridges in the Republic of Uzbekistan are reinforced concrete [4]. It should be noted that a significant number of currently operated bridge structures were built in 1960-1970. On fig. 1 shows a diagram of the construction of bridges by years.

Figure 1. Analysis of bridge construction by years

As can be seen from fig. 1, about 70% of the bridges operated on public roads of the republic have been in operation for more than 40 years. The diagram below shows that more than 36% of them (pre-accident and emergency) are unsatisfactory (Fig. 2).

Figure. 2 General condition of bridges operated on public roads of the Republic

From the given data (Fig. 2) it can be seen that 84% of bridges of international importance are in a satisfactory condition, however, the condition of bridges on urban and rural roads indicates the opposite. It follows from this that such a destructive state of bridge structures on highways is caused by the long service life of bridges and shortcomings in the system of their operation [5].

In modern cities, the design and construction of transport facilities is being actively carried out. To date, Tashkent is one of the major metropolitan areas, the traffic intensity and traffic flow have increased by 2-3 times, and more than 700-800 thousand cars pass through the streets of the city per day [6,7].

On fig. 3 shows a comparison of the location of bridge structures on the roads of international and national importance of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the context of territories.

Figure. 3. Comparison of bridge structures of international and national importance in the context of territories in the republic

As can be seen from the figure, the city of Tashkent differs from other regions of the Republic and the Republic of Karakalpakstan in the number of bridge structures of national importance by more than 1.65 times. In turn, this indicates the need for regular monitoring of bridge structures in the city of Tashkent.

According to the UE "Research Institute of Automobile Roads" of the Republic of Uzbekistan, there are more than 300 bridges in Tashkent, of which the main part (216 bridges, about 70%) are under the jurisdiction of the "Main Department for the Improvement of the Special Directorate for Operation, Maintenance and Repair artificial structures of cities and regions [8]. On fig. Table 4 shows balance holders in Tashkent and the number of bridges identified during the inventory.

Figure 4. The number of balance keepers of bridges in the city of Tashkent and identified in traffic

As of 2022, there are a total of 216 bridge structures in the "Local Government Improvement Department", which constitutes the main part of bridge structures [5]. It should be noted that the number of existing bridge structures is increasing dramatically (Figure 5). According to him, before 1990, the area of bridge constructions was 736,599 m², and after the years of independence, we can see that this figure has doubled.

Figure 5. Growth dynamics of the total area of operational bridge structures in Tashkent

As can be seen from the graph, the area of bridge structures under construction in our city is growing. According to the results of monitoring, the condition of most of the bridges that have been in use for 25-50 years of independence is unsatisfactory, as shown in Figures 6-7.

Figure 6. Corrosion in the beam and beam of overpasses in the city of Tashkent

Figure 7. Defects in the carriageway and deformation joints of overpasses in Tashkent

Conclusion. In order to eliminate this problem, the following steps should be taken

- researching the technical status of reinforced concrete bridge shots in operation in Tashkent;
- analysis of features of active monitoring of urban reinforced concrete bridge designs in developed countries;
- consideration and analysis of negative factors and effects in the assessment of the technical condition of urban reinforced concrete bridge structures;
- in the research methods, the technological condition of the bridge canvas is evaluated in the conditions of traffic of cars on the bridge through natural experiments and mathematical modeling;
- development of a methodology for pre-prediction of the technical-operational condition of urban reinforced concrete bridge structures and its assessment;
- development of the informational electronic platform "Digital bridge monitoring" of urban bridge structures.

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